

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 30, No. 7

Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the seventh regular issue of 2024. In this issue, 5 papers by 12 authors from 6 countries - Brazil, Ecuador, Germany, Iraq, Spain, Turkey - cover various topical aspects of computer science. In a continuous effort to further strengthen our journal, I would like to expand the editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a strong publication record, you are welcome to apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and trends.

As always, I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research and the editorial board and guest reviewers for their extremely valuable review effort and suggestions for improvement. I also want to thank the readers for their interest in our articles, which is reflected in the consistently high number of user accesses and PDF downloads. These contributions, together with the generous support of the consortium members, maintain the quality of our journal.

In the seventh regular issue, I am very pleased to present the following 5 accepted articles: Vinicius Bischoff and Kleinner Farias from Brazil report their study on a controlled experiment with 22 participants (15 students, 7 professionals) in which the correctness and the effort required for the integration of feature models were investigated. Abdulkadir Buldu, Kaplan Kaplan and Melih Kuncan from Turkey present their research on an assistive system based on EEG data and Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT), which aims to reduce the life-threatening risk for epilepsy patients. In a collaboration between researchers from Ecuador and Spain, Darwin Alulema, Maximiliano Paredes-Velasco and Ricardo de Arriba Lasso report in their manuscript on the LESCA system, which performs adaptive content feedback through scaffolding and supports the development of high-level competencies. In another joint research between colleagues from Iraq and Germany, Anwar Mira and Olaf Hellwich present their approach to improve recognition capabilities by optimizing deep learning features for hand gesture image recognition. Specifically, they propose to enhance features of well-trained DNNs using an improved radial basis function (RBF) neural network, targeting recognition within individual gesture categories.

And last but not least, Rasim Çekik and Mahmut Kaya from Turkey propose in their research a new performance metric to evaluate filter feature selection methods in text classification.

Enjoy Reading!

Best regards,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
Email: c.guetl@tugraz.at